

Neural Network Inversion Of Bidirectional Reflectance

J. A. Smith, J. A. Pedelty and R. G. Knox
 NASA Goddard Space Flight Center
 Greenbelt, MD 20771
 (301) 286-4950
 FAX: (301) 286-1757

ABSTRACT

A Monte Carlo canopy reflectance model for predicting canopy bidirectional reflectance is coupled to a forest ecosystem dynamics succession model. The combined models are being applied to forest canopies in order to train a back propagation artificial neural network to extract underlying canopy biophysical attributes or forest succession stage. Validation of the modeling approach and neural network inversion performance is carried out for field data collected at the Northern Experimental Forest study site near Howland, Maine, the location of a NASA sponsored Forest Ecosystem Dynamics Multi-sensor Aircraft Campaign.

INTRODUCTION

An active area of research is the combined use of physically based remote sensing models and neural network approaches to extract biogeophysical parameters from remote sensing observations (Dawson and Fung 1993). For example, Tsang, et al. (1992) used a neural network trained with a multiple scattering model to infer snow parameters from passive microwave remote sensing measurements and, similarly, Smith (1993) employed a simple multiple scattering model to train a backpropagation neural network for leaf area index estimation for sparse density canopies using optical reflective measurements.

This paper describes ongoing work which extends our earlier studies in several directions. We are now employing a more sophisticated Monte Carlo reflectance model to model dense forest canopies, as compared to the use of a simple two-stream model applied to sparse canopies, and are coupling this model to a forest succession model which provides many of the theoretical inputs to the reflectance calculations.

FORWARD MODELING PROBLEM

Forest Succession Model

The Forest Ecosystem Dynamics model described by Levine, et al (1993; see also Smith and Urban 1988; Urban 1990) was used to compute the canopy geometrical parameters required for the bi-directional reflectance modeling, described later, as a function of site index and succession stage. This is a stochastic gap model which simulates the establishment, annual diameter growth, and mortality of each tree on a small model plot which is defined by the primary zone of influence of a single canopy-dominant tree. Each tree in the plot is labeled by species, size and recent growth history. The basic individual tree growth equation is given by:

$$\frac{d(D^2H)}{dt} = R * LA \frac{(1 - DH)}{D_{max}H_{max}} \quad (1)$$

where D is tree diameter, H tree height, R is a species-dependent growth parameter, LA is the leaf area and D_{max} and H_{max} are the maximum diameter and height for a given species.

Three successional trajectories were modeled for the study area described below, representing relatively dry, mesic, and wet soil conditions. For each soil, five age classes, 25, 50, 75, 100, and 200 years were identified for reflectance modeling. Tree species abundances in each successional stage were represented by a mix of Conifer, C, Shade Tolerant, ST, or Shade Intolerant, SI, species in different proportions in a two-layer canopy. Fifteen model replications were run for each successional trajectory. For each model calculation, the Leaf Area Index for each species mix for each layer were computed for input into the reflectance model. Fig. 1 shows the total Leaf Area Index for the five age classes corresponding to the mesic site.

Fig. 1

Monte Carlo Reflectance Model

The SRVC (Solar Radiation Vegetation Canopy) Monte Carlo reflectance model (Smith and Oliver 1974) was used, after some modification, to predict canopy bi-directional reflectance factors. The basic model is shown schematically in Fig. 2. The canopy is assumed to be composed of inhomogeneous layers of Lambertian scatterers of known optical properties, statistical composition and geometrical arrangement and bounded by a soil reflecting background. Incident radiation is composed of direct solar and diffuse sky flux sources partitioned into 10 degree by 20 degree azimuthal sectors. Interaction of these sources with canopy and soil scattering elements generate new radiation sources which may further interact with canopy/soil elements. All upward and downward flux interactions are iteratively traced through the canopy system until the level of flux in all source directions within all canopy layers fall below user-selected thresholds.

Fig. 2

The interaction probability in any canopy layer, P_{hit} , for a given source direction, θ_r , is given by:

$$P_o(\theta_r) = \left(1 - s \frac{g(\theta_r)}{\sin(\theta_r)} \right)^{\frac{LAI}{s}} \quad (2)$$

$$P_{hit} = (1 - P_o)$$

where s , ranging from 0 to 1, is an index of canopy density, LAI is leaf area index, θ_i is the source inclination angle and g is the mean canopy projection in the source direction and depends upon the foliage inclination angle distribution. These interaction probabilities can be calculated for any given canopy component within a layer. However, to compute the overall interaction probability within a canopy layer consisting of three species, i.e. Conifer, C, Shade Tolerant, ST, or Shade Intolerant, SI, the individual interaction probabilities must be combined as follows:

$$P_{hit}(C \text{ or } ST \text{ or } SI) = P_{hit}(C) + P_{hit}(ST) + P_{hit}(SI) - P_{hit}(S)P_{hit}(ST) - P_{hit}(S)P_{hit}(SI) - P_{hit}(ST)P_{hit}(SI) \quad (3)$$

Finally, the basic scattering elements for Shade Intolerant and Shade Tolerant, i.e. hardwood species, were taken to be individual leaves and these are the optical properties employed. However, for Conifers, needle cluster or branch level optical properties (Williams 1991) were modeled and employed. For each successional stage, 400 trials of the reflectance model were run.

NEURAL NETWORK INVERSION

Study site

Analyses of the coupled Monte Carlo Reflectance and Stochastic forest succession models are being carried out at the International Paper Northern Experimental Forest study site near Howland, Maine. The site is located at approximately 45° 15' N latitude and 68° 45' W longitude and is the location of the NASA Forest Ecosystem Dynamics Multi-sensor Aircraft Campaign (Smith, et al., 1990). The area comprises approximately 7000 ha containing several intensive experimental sites, where detailed ecological and mensuration measurements have been obtained. It contains an assortment of small plantations, multi-generation clearings, and large natural forest stands. Because of distinct management programs, useful historical background on specific areas is available. The natural stands in this boreal - northern hardwood transitional forest consist of hemlock-spruce-fir, aspen-birch, and hemlock-hardwood mixtures. Topographically, the region varies from flat to gently rolling, with a maximum elevation change of less than 135 m. Due to the region's glacial history, soil drainage classes within a small area may vary widely, from well drained to poorly drained. Consequently, an elaborate patchwork of forest communities has developed, supporting exceptional diversity in forest structure.

Coupled Model Results

Atmospherically corrected, multispectral imagery was collected by the Airborne Visible / Infrared Imaging Spectrometer (AVIRIS) over the test area during the summer of 1990 (Lawrence, et al 1994). Six regions of relatively homogeneous cover were identified in the images corresponding to 50 year dry, 75 and 200 year mesic and 50, 100 and 200 year wet successional stages. For each area, AVIRIS measurements from nine adjacent pixels (three by three blocks) were extracted. Spectral bidirectional reflectance distribution functions were computed using geometrical properties, e.g. leaf area index profiles by species mix in a two layer canopy, computed from the forest succession model.

The results for the 50 year, dry site are given below where the solid lines correspond to the mean plus and minus the standard deviation of the predicted Monte Carlo reflectance results. The individual dashed lines correspond to the nine measured AVIRIS spectra. There is a general over prediction, especially in the visible wavelengths, with more comparable results obtained in the infrared

region. Some of the plots yielded better results, others were worse. The forest dynamics model predictions are currently being field checked. These initial comparisons are actually encouraging since the predicted curves are computed from two independent, theoretical models driven by theoretical inputs. The results also offer an opportunity to examine the basic assumptions in the two models and to extend the models to account for the differences. For example, we are currently looking at including spatial inhomogeneity in the horizontal direction for the reflectance calculations.

Fig. 3

LAI Estimation

The use of a standard backpropagation (BP) neural network architecture, including adaptive learning, is being investigated to infer biogeophysical attributes or succession stage from bidirectional reflectance distribution functions. Preliminary tests using a BP with one hidden layer to infer succession stage from leaf area index profile by species were performed and yielded 80% recognition on training data. Earlier work had shown that a BP with only two input nodes corresponding to green reflectance and NDVI, and one hidden layer could predict total Leaf Area Index for sparse canopies (Smith 1993). The model data were divided into training and test sets. Ten replicates of the succession stage data were using for training and 5 replicates for testing. Initial results on the test data using this approach for a BP with one hidden layer with 7 nodes and employing a sigmoid function connecting inputs to hidden layer and a simple scaling activation function from hidden layer to the output layer consisting of one node correspond to total canopy Leaf Area Index are shown in Fig. 4. The results are shown after 6000 iterations. While overall 85% of the samples had errors less than 30 percent, the overall error rate is unacceptable and further work is continuing using the complete bidirectional distribution function.

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REFERENCES

- Dawson, M.S. and A.K. Fung, "Neural Networks and Their Applications to Parameter Retrieval and Classification." *IEEE Geosci. and Remote Sen. Newsletter*, (Sept. 1993):6-14.
- Lawrence, W.T. et al, "Comparative Analysis of Data Acquired by Three Narrow-Band Airborne Spectroradiometers over Subboreal Vegetation." *Remote Sens. Environ.*, vol 47 (1994):204-215.

Levine, E.R. et al, "Forest Ecosystem Dynamics: Linking Forest Succession, Soil Process and Radiation Models." *Ecological Modeling*, vol 65 (1993): 199-219.

Smith, T.M. and D. Urban, 1988. "Scale and Resolution of Forest Structural Pattern." *Vegetatio* 74:143-150.

Smith, J.A. and R.E. Oliver, "Effects of Changing Canopy Directional Reflectance on Feature Selection." *Applied Optics*, vol 13 (1974):1599-1604.

Smith, J.A. et al, "Sensor-fusion Field Experiment in Forest Ecosystem Dynamics." *Proc. SPIE Int. Soc. Opt. Eng.*, vol 1300 (1990):117-132.

Smith, J.A., "LAI Inversion Using a Back-Propagation Neural Network Trained with a Multiple Scattering Model." *IEEE Trans. on Geosci. and Remote Sen.*, vol 31, No. 5 (1993):1102-1106.

Tsang, L. et al, "Inversion of Snow Parameters from Passive Microwave Remote Sensing Measurements by a Neural Network Trained with a Multiple Scattering Model." *IEEE Trans. on Geosci. and Remote Sen.*, vol 30, No. 5 (1992):1015-1024.

Urban, D.L. 1990, "A Versatile Model to Simulate Forest Pattern: A User's Guide to ZELIG, Version 1.0." Environmental Sciences Department, University of Virginia, Charlottesville, VA.

Williams, D.L., "A Comparison of Spectral Reflectance Properties at the Needle, Branch, and Canopy Level for Selected Conifer Species." *Remote Sens. Environ.*, vol 35 (1991):79-93.

Fig. 4